

Evaluation of the Role of Intra-Articular Platelet Rich Plasma Injection in Peri-Arthritis Shoulder

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Abstract:

Background: Periarthritis shoulder is a disabling disease characterized by shoulder pain and limitations of both active and passive range of movement in all directions. It is the result of fibrosis and thickening of the joint capsule and adherence to the humeral head. Periarthritis can be managed using a variety of therapeutic techniques. Platelets rich plasma (PRP) is a concentrated platelet solution that degranulates alpha granules and includes a variety of growth factors, including cytokines that aid in soft tissue healing.

Objective: The aim of the study was to evaluate the role of intra-articular PRP injection in patients with shoulder peri-arthritis.

Methods: 31 patients (>40 year) with U/L or B/L frozen shoulder having pain more than or equal to two months were included. Shoulder mobilization was performed under short GA and full range of motion was achieved during the procedure followed by intra-articular injection of PRP (3ml) under all aseptic precaution with 20-gauge needle. Patients were reviewed & evaluated clinically on the basis of VAS and CSS score after 0, 2 and 4 weeks.

Results: The mean age of the patients was 57.58 ± 8.67 years with predominance of females (64.5%). The mean duration of pain was 6.03 ± 4.18 months. There was a significant decrease ($p=0.001^*$) in mean VAS scores at both 2- and 4-weeks post-treatment. Following the initiation of PRP therapy, there was a significant increase ($p=0.001^*$) in the mean CSS score at 2- and 4-weeks post-treatment.

Conclusion: Our study concluded that there was significant improvement in the pain as well as functional score after the PRP injection. Intra-articular PRP injection therapy with manipulation is a safe and effective treatment modality for periarthritis shoulder.

Keywords: Periarthritis, Shoulder pain, Platelets rich plasma, VAS score, CSS score.

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Introduction

Periarthritis shoulder, also known as adhesive capsulitis is characterized by shoulder pain and limitations of both active and passive range of movement in all directions. It is the result of fibrosis and thickening of the joint capsule and adherence to the humeral head [1]. Periarthritis is categorized into two types including the primary periarthritis which is also called as idiopathic and usually occurs in the absence of any history of trauma or trigger event whereas secondary periarthritis is usually encountered after periarticular trauma, fracture, or glenohumeral joint dislocation [2]. Recent research indicates that prevalence of periarthritis range between 2-5% in the general population [3]. In most cases, the symptoms go away on their own within a year or three. Generally it appear normal on

radiography or calcific deposits in the capsular periarticular tissue may be seen [4]. Mild pain in the shoulder joint are typical symptoms of periarthritis shoulder which gradually progressed with time and loss of mobility occurs at the glenohumeral joint [5]. Precise pathogenesis of periarthritis is yet unknown. Pain and stiffness in the glenohumeral joint capsule contracture primarily caused by increasing fibrosis. Adhesions of the synovial membrane of the shoulder joint, reactive fibrosis, and inflammation are other possible pathophysiological change. Subacromial fibrosis, proliferative synovitis, and thickening of the capsule may also be responsible for pathogenesis [6]. Periarthritis can be managed using a variety of therapeutic techniques. The goal of therapy is to reduce shoulder joint discomfort and limited

mobility. Analgesics, physical and rehabilitative medicine involving stretching exercises, hydro-dissection, minimally invasive intra-articular injections, manipulation under anaesthesia, invasive operations like arthroscopic or open synovectomy, and capsular releases are some of these therapies. These can be used separately or in conjunction to improve treatment therapy. All of these therapies help patients with their symptoms, but they have little impact on the pathoanatomic of the illness [7].

The use of platelet-rich plasma (PRP) in the treatment of periarthritis has been studied recently. PRP, as its name implies, is a concentrated platelet solution that degranulates alpha granules and includes a variety of growth factors, including cytokines that aid in soft tissue healing and platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β), fibroblast growth factor (FGF), hepatocyte growth factor (HGF), and epithelial growth factor (EGF) [8]. Centrifugation has substantially simplified PRP creation, making it suitable for usage in hospital environment with limited infrastructure. Given its safety and the availability of improved tools for outpatient preparation and delivery, PRP use has expanded in past decade [9].

Material and Methods

This observational consisted 31 patients (>40 year) with U/L or B/L frozen shoulder having pain more than or equal to two months who underwent Shoulder mobilization followed by intra-articular injection of platelet rich plasma in Himalayan hospital between April 2022 till April 2023. All patients were subjected to routine haematological investigation (Hb, TLC, DLC, Platelet count, Random Blood Sugar and Serum Creatinine) and radiological investigation (AP and axial view of Shoulder). Shoulder mobilization was performed under short GA and full range of motion was achieved during the procedure followed by intra-articular injection of PRP(3ml) under all aseptic precaution with 20-gauge needle. After 8 hours patients were discharged on Analgesics and Active ROM exercises were advised to the patients. Patients were reviewed & evaluated clinically on the basis of VAS and CSS score after 0, 2 and 4 weeks.

Results

The mean age of the patients was 57.58 ± 8.67 years. Among total 31 patients, 6 (19.4%) patients belong to age group of 41-50 years, 15 (48.4%) patients belong to age group of 51-60 years, 7 (22.6%) patients belong to age group of 61-70 years, and 3 (9.7%) patients belong to age group of 71-80 years. There was a notable predominance of females, comprising 64.5% (20 individuals), while males accounted for 35.5% (11 individuals) (Table 1).

Table 1: Division of number of patients according to age and gender

Variable	Domain	Mean or Number	SD or Percent
Mean age		57.58 Yrs	8.67 Yrs
Age groups	41-50	6	19.4
	51-60	15	48.4
	61-70	7	22.6
	71-80	3	9.7
Gender	Male	11	35.5
	Female	20	64.5

Pain localization varied among the patients: 51.6% (16 individuals) reported pain in the right shoulder, 41.9% (13 individuals) in the left shoulder, and 6.5% (2 individuals) experienced discomfort in both shoulders simultaneously. The mean duration of

pain was 6.03 ± 4.18 months. Seven (22.6 %) patients reported with pain duration < 3 months in patients, while more than half patients (51.6%) had pain for 4-6 months. Only 2 patients had pain for more than one year (Table 2).

Table 2: Division of number of patients according to duration of and site of pain at presentation

Variable	Domain	Mean or Number	SD or Percent
Site of Pain	Right Shoulder	16	51.6
	Left Shoulder	13	41.9
	B/L Shoulder	2	6.5
Mean pain duration		6.03 months	4.18 months
Duration of pain	0-3 months	7	22.6
	4-6 months	16	51.6
	7-9 Months	5	16.1
	10-12 Months	1	3.2
	>12 Months	2	6.5

The severity of pain, as measured by VAS scores, significantly decreased ($p=0.001^*$) after platelet-rich plasma (PRP) therapy. Initially, 30 (96.8%) patients reported severe pain, which decreased to a moderate level in the same percentage of patients

after 2 weeks of treatment. After 4 weeks, 24 (77.4%) patients experienced a further reduction to mild pain. These findings indicate the progressive effectiveness of PRP therapy in alleviating pain severity (Table 3).

Table 3: Mean Visual Analogue Score (VAS) at 2- and 4-Weeks follow-up

Pain	Mild (VAS \leq 3)	Moderate (VAS=3.5-6.4)	Severe (VAS \geq 6.5)	P Value
Pre-procedure	0	1 (3.2%)	30 (96.8%)	0.001*
At 2 weeks	0	30 (96.8%)	1 (3.2%)	
At 4 weeks	24 (77.4%)	7 (22.6%)	0	

Visual analogue score was noted at various contact points. The mean VAS score was 8.58 ± 0.76 before the start of procedure. Following the intervention (PRP therapy), there was a significant decrease

($p=0.0018$) in mean VAS scores at both 2- and 4-weeks post-treatment. At 2 weeks, scores averaged 5.74 ± 1.03 , further decreasing to 2.80 ± 1.04 by 4 weeks (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Mean Visual Analogue Score (VAS) at various contact points

Before platelet-rich plasma (PRP) therapy, all patients (31) had poor shoulder mobility according to the Constant-Murley Shoulder Score (CSS). After two weeks of treatment, mobility increased to a fair level in 5 (16.1%) patients, and after four weeks, it improved to fair and good levels in 17 (54.8%) and 3 (9.7%) patients, respectively. These findings demonstrate significant improvement in shoulder mobility following PRP therapy (Table 4).

Table 4: Constant Shoulder Score (CSS) at 2 and 4 weeks follow up

CSS	Poor (CSS $<$ 56)	Fair (CSS=56-70)	Good (CSS=71-85)	P Value
Pre-procedure	31 (100%)	0	0	0.001*
At 2 weeks	26 (83.9%)	5 (16.1%)	0	
At 4 weeks	11 (35.5%)	17 (54.8%)	3 (9.7%)	

The mean Constant-Murley Shoulder Score (CSS) was 23.81 ± 8.12 before the commencement of the procedure. Following the initiation of PRP therapy, there was a significant increase in the mean CSS score. Specifically, at 2 weeks of treatment, the

mean CSS score rose to 48.81 ± 8.50 , indicating notable improvement. This improvement continued, with a further increase observed at 4 weeks of treatment, where the mean CSS score reached 59.39 ± 8.39 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Mean Constant Shoulder Score (CSS)

Discussion

The present study entitled “Evaluation of the role of intra-articular platelet rich plasma injection in periarthritis shoulder” was conducted in the Department of Orthopaedics, Himalayan Institute of Medical Sciences, and Dehradun. A total of 31 patients were included in our study. All enrolled participants were administered intra-articular Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) injections subsequent to manipulation under General Anaesthesia.

In this study, 31 patients with shoulder periarthritis with ages ranging from 41 to 80 years were included. The highest incidence was reported in the age group of 51-60 years representing 48.4% of patients. Similar results have been reported by the Gupta et al. which found that the incidence of the periarthritis shoulder was higher in the fifth decade of life (46.67%) [1]. The result was similar to previous studies conducted by Kothari et al. [10] and Neviasser et al. [5]. The mean age of the patients included in the study was 57.58 ± 8.67 years which corroborated with the findings of Gupta et al in which mean age of periarthritis patients was 47.25 ± 8.38 years [1]. Kothari et al. also had a similar age range in their study population (mean age 51.9 ± 10.1 years) [10].

In present study, a higher female to male ratio was encountered in the incidence of periarthritis. Previous study by Gupta et al. also reported that periarthritis mostly occurred in female patients than males [1]. Similar observations have been made in the previous study by Sheridan et al. [11]. Upadhyay et al. [12] and Kothari et al. [10] also reported female predominance. However, in the study by Somisetty et al. males are found to be more affected with the periarthritis than females [13]. In present study, site of pain in right and shoulder was almost similar (51.6% vs 41.9%). However, in the previous study

by Gupta et al. side of the joint affected by periarthritis was higher on the non-dominant side (63.33%) [1]. Upadhyay et al. also reported higher involvement of the non-dominant side compared to the dominant side [12]. In the study by Kothari et al. majority of patients had involvement of dominant side (58.9%) [10].

The mean duration of pain in current study was 6.03 ± 4.18 months with most of patients (51.6%) experiencing the pain from 4-6 months. In the study by Somisetty et al. most of patients experienced pain for 6-12 months [13].

In the present study, the mean VAS score was 8.58 ± 0.76 before the start of platelet-rich plasma (PRP) therapy and VAS score was found to be decrease significantly 2 and 4 weeks of treatment (5.74 ± 1.03 and 2.80 ± 1.04). Pain severity was significantly decrease from severe to moderate and mild level 2-4 weeks of treatment. Similar observations have been made by Gupta et al. in which VAS score showed a linear declining trend from baseline to 24 weeks of treatment [1]. PRP was shown to be more effective than corticosteroid injection in improving pain and disability scores after 12 weeks in a research by Barman et al. [14]. Similar to our findings in the PRP group, Ünlü et al. assessed the effectiveness of IA PRP injection over normal saline in controlling FS and discovered increases in SPADI score and decreases in VAS score [15].

The mean CSS score was 23.81 ± 8.12 before the start of platelet-rich plasma (PRP) therapy and CSS score was found to be significantly increase at 2 weeks and 4 of treatment (48.81 ± 8.50 and 59.39 ± 8.39). The mobility was significantly increase from poor to fair and good level after 4 weeks of treatment. According to Upadhyay et al., PRP injections provided pain alleviation and enhanced shoulder function over the course of around 12

weeks [12]. Similar results to this study were also reported by Aslani et al., who evaluated the effectiveness of PRP in treating frozen shoulder and showed improvements in ROM, a decrease in shoulder pain, and an improvement in the QuickDASH score [16].

Findings of present study regarding the increase of shoulder mobility and pain reduction following PRP therapy may be explained by the possibility that PRP improves all stages of tissue repair, including the proliferative, remodelling, and inflammatory phases of capsular healing in periarthritis. PRP acts as a growth factor agonist and possesses chemotactic and mitogenic qualities. Large doses of growth factors, anti-inflammatory drugs, and activated platelets change the inflammatory and healing cascades, reversing the degenerative process [13].

Conclusion

In our study of 31 cases of Periarthritis shoulder, mobilized under GA, were administered intra-articular PRP injections. On the basis of this study, it can be concluded that there was significant improvement in the pain as well as functional score after the PRP injection.

Intra-articular PRP injection therapy with manipulation is a safe and effective treatment modality for periarthritis shoulder.

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